

Exploring the Role and Importance of Career Counselling in Developing Awareness of Graduate Students' Career Choices during Corvid 19

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Abstract

This study explores the role and importance of career counseling in developing awareness of career choices at the university level. The main focus of the study was to find out the role and importance of career counselling from an Islamic perspective; also, the related aspects regarding the topic were discussed. A description of the research participants, the benefits of career counseling, the challenges that career counseling can overcome, and research method considerations are also included. This study was an empirical examination of qualitative perceptions due to the nature of the problem. After examining the research's purpose, this study was selected for its depth and detail in studying the identified subjects. Data were gathered through focus group interviews to help develop conversational relationships with the students. Ten focus groups were conducted with graduate students of sciences and social sciences. Ten focus groups having 5 students each were selected from various university faculties. Data indicates career counselling at the university level provides good career orientation, connects students with industry, builds confidence, and paves the way for their future. The majority of the students from the focus group data responded that career counseling shows directions about unemployment and give correct incentive. The majority of the students expressed the difficulties and lack of career counseling centers after getting a certain degree. Due to the present Covid-19 Scenario, career counselling is still helpful in developing awareness in students about career services and further impact on their career choices.

Introduction

Counseling or consultation is part of human nature, an essential pillar of the Islamic way of life and is considered one of the best attributes of believers. Adopting a system of counseling is essential for a prosperous and peaceful life. Counseling is a source of goodness, prosperity, and descent of mercy. Consultation for livelihood is called career counseling. According to Post, Borgen, Amundsen, & Washburn Post et al. (2002), There are four main parts to career counseling: (1) assisting individuals in developing more self-awareness in areas such as interests, values, abilities, and personality type; (2) linking students to resources to obtain a better understanding of jobs and occupations (3) assisting individuals to be active managers of their career paths by involving them in the decision-making process so that they can choose a career path that is well suited to their interests, values, abilities, and personality style, and (4) assisting students in the decision-making process so that they can choose a career path that is well suited to their interests, values, abilities, and personality style.

The domains of education and employment are continuously shifting due to the high speed of technological advancement in modern times. Education patterns are rapidly shifting. Careers and livelihoods are the most affected by this transition. Children are experiencing psychological issues, including depression and dissatisfaction, as a result of the fast-changing situation. New curricula are being developed at universities, and new occupations that did not exist previously are being created. Today's students are confronted with a bewildering array of educational and professional options. This frequently leads to a state of perplexity that must be rectified. There is no perfect guidance in choosing study subjects and no proper planning for employment, especially in small places.

Career counseling is an essential tool to deal with these challenges and provide proper advice on choosing livelihood from an Islamic perspective. Exceptionally professional or career counselling assists students in determining their career objectives by examining their interests and abilities. The field of career counselling is vast. However, the focus of this research is to emphasize the role and importance of career counselling for university students from an Islamic perspective because the University is an institution where students are directed to move into the practice area and work for a livelihood exact after completing their studies

or in some cases during the studies. So that, at the university level, students requires the most career counseling. It is necessary to draw the authorities' attention to this critical issue and to work with them to establish well-equipped career counseling departments in Pakistani educational institutions, as well as to offer suggestions for how students, teachers, and parents can receive career guidance from an Islamic perspective through the Quran and Sunnah as well as various platforms from the universities which can provide motivation and guidance. As given, the study seeks out graduate students' career choices and how career counseling services impact their vision.

Moreover, a career is subject to improve livelihood. Human behavior, life approaches, and social awareness all changed dramatically during the twentieth century and after COVID 19. These developments have far-reaching ramifications for people throughout the world. Despite the many benefits of this procedure, many people have difficulty understanding concerns related to advisory services, which directly and indirectly affect their objectives in terms of livelihood. This issue emphasizes the relevance and requirement for research in this field. As stated in the title, the purpose of this study is to investigate the role and importance of career counseling from an Islamic perspective, particularly at the university level. The purpose and benefit of working on this research were to understand the importance of career counseling. People will realize that career counseling services are available and better understand their choices in choosing a career path.

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate the understanding of Career Counselling.
2. To investigate the students understanding of Career Counselling in developing career choices at the university level.
3. To explore the difficulties in Career Counselling process in developing career choices for graduate students.

Research Questions

1. What is the understanding of Career Counselling.
2. How do graduate students understanding of Career Counselling in developing career choices at the university level.
3. what are the difficulties in Career Counselling in developing career choices during *Covid-19 scenario* for graduate students.

Review of the Literature

Career counseling assists individuals in choosing appropriate educational and occupational choices and making career options based on future employment demands and requirements. As discussed above in detail about counseling or consultation, career counseling is a consultation about livelihood. The word career counseling has been defined in various dictionaries and by people, some of which are as follows:

According to the Cambridge Business English Dictionary

“Assistance and information on what type of career someone would be able to do or how they might advance to a better job” (Cambridge Business English Dictionary)

According to Oxford Learners Dictionary

“Counsel someone to listen to and provide assistance or professional guidance to someone who requires assistance.”

(https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/counsel_2?q=counselling)

According to Merriam-Webster

“Individual professional advice through the use of psychological procedures, particularly in the collection of case history data, the use of specific methodologies of the individual interviews, and the assessment of interests and abilities” (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/counselling>)

Career counseling comprises a wide variety of professional activities that assist people in overcoming career-related obstacles. Adolescents interested in exploring career alternatives, experienced professionals considering a career switch, parents who wish to return to work after raising their child, and those looking for a job are all served by career counselors as Savickas is of the view about career counseling that exploration, making professional choices, managing job changes, lifetime career development, and dealing with various career-related concerns are all referred to as career counseling (Savickas, 2019). Likewise, Shertzer and Stone (1976) defined career counseling as a combination of Islamic and western approaches as “Counseling is the process of combining Islamic and western approaches to assist an individual in better understanding himself and his surroundings.” Six conceptually guidance entails the practice of a point of view to assist an individual as an educational construct. It relates to providing experiences that help students understand them, and it refers to the organization of procedures and processes to produce a helping connection as a service.

Career counseling is a one-on-one encounter between a practitioner and a client, usually continuous in which psychological theory and a set of communication skills are applied. The main goal is to assist the client in

making career-related decisions and resolving career-related problems (Kidd, 2006). In response to these societal changes, career counseling appears to be evolving into an interpretative field in which practitioners assist individuals in connecting their quest for meaning to the community's labor division. Also, career counseling is a sort of advice and support provided by career counselors to their clients to assist them in managing their life, learning, and work transitions (careers). Tahir (2018) defines career counseling as "exploring students' interests and guiding them to choose their professional vocation while taking into account their skills, shortcomings, resources, and possibilities.

Also, career counseling is considered a collection of career information materials structured for simple access, spanning a wide range of topics and providing various media delivery options (Sampson et al., 2004). Clients receive career coaching to help them identify themes and meanings in their own stories to take action in the direction they want to go. Client narratives reveal the subjective perspective of the counselor and client as co-collaborators in the counseling process: the focus is on the relationship and the procedure (Goldman, 1992).

Advantages of Career Counselling Services

Career counseling is frequently available to assist a person in obtaining suitable placements/jobs, resolving disputes with their employers, or locating other valuable services. Professional career counselors can help persons who are facing difficulties in their careers. They may place a person's qualifications, experience, strengths, and weaknesses in context using their knowledge of career development and job markets, while also considering their desired pay, personal hobbies and interests, geography, employment market, and educational options. Career counselors can also assist people in getting a better grasp of what means most to them individually, how to plan their careers independently, and how to make difficult decisions and get through times of crisis using their counseling and teaching skills (Savickas, 2019).

In the perspective of more dynamic and diverse field employment patterns, however, the notion of career counseling as a process of assisting people in making sensible professional decisions that place them on a specific job route for the rest of their lives is becoming increasingly appropriate (KIDD) 2007. Career counselors work with people of all ages and stages of their careers, assisting them with various career-related issues. Though work and academic options will undoubtedly be significant, many individuals may also require assistance with broader difficulties, such as dealing with the challenges of redundancy and unemployment, determining whether to return to school or work and balancing several life responsibilities, etc. Here, too, career counselling assists in dealing with such situations and finding new ways. Furthermore, clients' challenges early in the vocational counseling process may disguise underlying emotional issues that will not emerge evidently until later in the counseling process (KIDD) 2007. As a result, career counseling can be viewed as a process that assists individuals in making career-related decisions and effectively managing their careers throughout their lives and developing the emotional stability to deal with the challenges that come up as their working lives progress.

People who are facing career difficulties can benefit from professional career counseling. It can put a person's credentials, experiences, capabilities, and shortcomings in a broad context while also considering their desired wage, personal hobbies and interests, location, job market, and educational prospects, thanks to their knowledge in career development and labor markets (Savickas, 2019). In the career counselling procedure, the role of the counselor is also very significant. However, career counselors can assist people in getting a better awareness of what is important to them, how to plan their careers independently, and how to make difficult decisions and get through times of crisis using their counseling and teaching skills (Savickas, 2019). Finally, that policymakers in many nations openly subsidize career counseling services because of these numerous benefits. The European Union, for example, views career assistance and counseling as a tool for effectively combating social exclusion and improving individuals' employability.

Difficulties in Conducting Career Counselling

Career counseling is no doubt a beneficial and essential activity. Its advantages are apparent, and both Islam and modern technology support its benefits and procedures. Despite this, doing career counselling is still tricky, particularly in a developing country like Pakistan, where the notion of career counselling is still unclear. Career decision-making challenges are referred to as career decision-making taxonomies. The difficulty of making career decisions is referred to as career decision-making taxonomy. Making a career selection is a complicated process that requires decision-makers to analyze information about themselves and information about the workplace (Jepsen, 1984). Decision-makers may have difficulty making decisions if they lack valuable information, have conflicting information, or do not know how to interpret it (Gati, 1986).

Difficulties might also develop when an individual's psychological features interfere with decision-making activities (Crites, 1969). There are three subcategories to these issues: lack of preparation, insufficient information, and conflicting information. Individuals experiencing challenges in the process of career decision-

making are said to be lacking in preparedness. Lack of motivation, overall indecisiveness, and cognitive distortions all contribute to a lack of preparation. Less information refers to problems that arise when people make judgments based on insufficient knowledge. Learning disabled students drop out at a higher rate than their non-disabled counterparts. These young people express a more significant need for transition services that focus on career counseling and finding and keeping jobs. Instructional career counseling utilizing cognitive methodologies has been advocated (Billier, 1987).

The following are some of the most typical traits of adults with learning problems that may contribute to their challenges in professional development and necessitate counseling: Lack of professional maturity and self-awareness, Monitoring and evaluation skills that aren't well developed (Billier & Horn, 1991). Inability to solve problems, these people did not grasp how their specific impairments led to their challenges, particularly literacy (Hoffmann et al., 1987). Adults with learning difficulties find it difficult to get work when filling out application forms and making a good appearance in interviews. According to (Hoffmann et al., 1987), Adults said that a lack of social acceptance and a loss of temper were contributing factors in their inability to hold a job. People with learning difficulties, according to employers, have a bad attitude, are unreliable, and lack interpersonal skills. Furthermore, various statutes state that the Skill acquisition service and counseling are vital for the higher education organization (Sujadi et al., 2020). The present issue is that many higher education institutions still lack counseling services for university students who require assistance with personal, social, learning, and professional issues. Although several higher education institutions already exist, not all of them have established standard career procedures. As a result, students in higher education who have difficulties are unsure how to seek professional assistance; thus, some of them are determined to communicate their concerns with their friends and even on social networking websites (Azeem et al., 2021; Sujadi et al., 2020).

Additionally, the extended lockdown has significant negative psychological impacts on careers requiring counseling, such as posttraumatic stress symptoms, nervousness, psychological distress, wrath, and bewilderment. Frustration, anxieties, financial loss, and potential shame are factors that might cause these symptoms (Drosos et al., 2021; Zikra Faiz et al., 2021). Thus, to overcome these challenges, receive career guidance and participating in the career-development program during higher education is especially crucial for students with learning difficulties. These programs can assist individuals in choosing jobs that capitalize on their abilities while downplaying their deficiencies and assisting them in obtaining work by training them in job writing and interviewing skills. They may also deal with issues that develop on the job, such as interpersonal skills and anger management. Furthermore, career counselors, classroom teachers, and special educators can collaborate to develop a project that is tailored to the requirements.

Research Method

The objective of the interview is to learn more about my work, exploring the role and importance of Career Counselling to develop graduate students' career choices during COVID 19. Because structured interviews limit respondents' ability to express themselves in their own words, I chose the semi-structured focus group interview method. Focus groups were formed to get a complete picture of the student's perception of the role and importance of Career Counselling from an Islamic perspective at the university level. Focus groups Interviewers of a small group of students from various faculties were chosen to obtain in-depth data since it was necessary to understand how students thought in depth. As a result, having students share their observations and impressions regarding Career Counselling and remark on each other's understanding was critical for this research design. Twelve focus groups with five students were held through which I shortlisted the ten interviews whose opinions strongly supported my topic. They were chosen using a straightforward sampling method; as a result, a random sample of the group being chosen.

Each focus group's students were given a number to keep a record of their contributions. Whenever an answer was given, the respondent's number was recorded. Responses were categorized by group number and respondent number in this manner; for example, G1-S1 signifies student1 in group1. Student 3 in Group 4 is represented by G4-S3. Likewise, also focus group interviews helped me establish a verbal interaction with participants on their concept of Career Counselling from an Islamic perspective. As a result, the focus group interview was chosen for students' opinion as the most effective method since qualitative interviewing allowed interviewees to wholly and freely express their thoughts.

Because this research involved human individuals, various potential ethical considerations were carefully explored before and throughout the investigation. Their relationship may impact how the interviews are conducted and the quality of the information acquired. Participants should be treated with respect by the researcher, and the researcher should be open, straightforward, and honest with them. Due to the current Scenario of Covid-19, as a responsible citizen, I followed the SOPs given by the authorities during the interview procedures, and I also asked the interview participants to show their sense of responsibility by following the SOPs in this Scenario. I had a hand sanitizer and several extra masks in my bag at all times so that if any

interview participant did not follow the SOPs, I could sanitize him as needed and present him with a mask, ensuring that my interview process was not disrupted and that my health was not jeopardized. Finally, the data collection process took around ten weeks to complete.

Findings and Presentation of Focus Group Data

The following were the main themes and sub-themes that emerged from the student's data:

Theme 1: Understanding of Counselling

Theme 2: Advantages of Career Counselling

Theme 3: Difficulties counseling can overcome

Theme 1: Understanding of Counselling Process

Before knowing the understanding of career counseling, I asked the participants about their understanding of the counseling. The purpose of asking this question was to know their perception of counseling and also this question further leads to my topic. Here is the summary of the quotes of those participants' who gave their perception about counseling is as *few focus group participants commented about their perceptions of counseling as below:*

Counselling gives us a thought of a trainer who will train someone in one direction. (F4-S1)

Moreover, one student stated that counseling is a consultation with an expert person: Counseling to consult an expert about your interests and expertise or give a guideline for any job. (F2-S2)

Another student from F7 added as: *An expert person uses his experience to solve someone's problems that the person himself could not understand is Counselling. (F7-S2)*

Students also commented that it's a kind of discussion that guides the benefits and disadvantages of things as:

Counseling is to tell the benefits and disadvantages of things. (F4-S2)

Another stated:

There is a kind of discussion in which a counselor listens to your problems and tells you the solution. (F6-S1)

Thus, the above responses indicated that students have a clear understanding of counseling that taking advice and consulting with experience persons about matters is counseling. Moreover, counseling means explaining and guiding to understand one's desire and need and then give them some positive direction for their plan.

Career counseling is a kind of guideline one has to use to manage their livelihood. There are two parts of Career Counselling. The first is related to students' issues regarding education which later link with careers and the second is related to the source of income, whether it is a job or business etc. The majority of student participants were apparent in their perception of career counselling. They gave mixed views. For example, one student stated:

Consultation to go into an appropriate field according to one's ability is Career Counselling. (F4-S1)

Another student from the same group stated: *Career counseling means to show someone a direction about employment that matches their personality and environment. (F4-S5)*

Likewise, students stated that: *Give correct motivation to choose any field is career counseling. (F3-S3)*

Another said: *Career counseling means analyzing before entering some specific field whether you are perfect for this field of study or not. (F9-S2)*

Likewise, few participants were of the view that career counseling equips with some technical tools:

Career Counselling equips someone with some technical tools or job search methods. (F1-S1)

Another student said: *Career counseling refers to the struggle to find legitimate ways to make money. (F7-S1)*

Finally, it was summed up through the above quotes that several responses were only expressed unusually. Few participants felt that career counseling *gives the confidence to choose a career according to one's ability*; one stated that "it *breaks the stalemate*" and "*prepares youth for the industry.*" Other particular responses involved abilities, interests, a career being made up of multiple professions, and doing what others anticipate from you. In conclusion, "Career counseling" is a network; it is a planned activity, it's a combined process or activity where institutes and individuals play their role equally to get more job opportunities, enable one for perfect means of earning, and get *a person out of failure*. Thus, it was concluded that most students believed that the major objective and main purpose of career counseling is to enable an individual for a successful and positive adjustment in society, whether at the individual level, social level, academic level, or professional level. Also, check the person's hidden abilities through conversation and guide him either he is a good marketer, a finance person; a lawman, etc., and facilitate him through creative career ideas.

Theme 3: Role and Importance of Career Counselling at the University Level

The one objective of my research is to understand the perceptions of university-level and students about the role and importance of careers counselling at the university level. Therefore, this theme examines this perception.

Also, theme 3 is essential because there has been a lot of work done in career counselling at the initial levels worldwide before, but not much has been done to know its role and importance in higher education levels. People opinion about the role and importance of career counselling at university levels, especially in backward areas of Pakistan, is not so clear. Therefore, I decided to work at the university level to find it out. A variety of views emerged on this theme; student participants strongly emphasized its importance at the university level and no one denied it. For example, *University level student is more mature and is more sensitive for future. That is the place he needs to give complete knowledge about careers.* (F4-S1)

Another stated:

University-level counseling provides the basis for our future; it shows us those ways and means we don't know. (F7-S1)

Thus, it is summed up that university-level career counseling creates such qualities in an individual that he can take up things, solve problems intelligently and become beneficial for the company or institutes in his professional life as F4-S3, F7-S1 stated. Alleviate an individual's worries about his future and give him proper direction while removing his conflicts about his career etc. This is the point where the need to develop creative thinking and ideas through communication and techniques of analysis with complete equipment has to give at this level to enhance and build up mental independence and confidence for the practical life. Moreover, the teacher gives career motivation to the students through the free flow of information so that the student does not get scared but clear their confusions about a career by asking more and more questions.

This theme includes students' responses on the advantages of getting career counseling at the university level. There were numerous themes fabricated in this category though the participants favored the career counseling process. For example, one said: *Career counseling gives you the right direction for the future. Career counseling makes your work fruitful. If there is no one to guide and motivate you, maybe you will not be able to choose your field the same way as a career counseling person.* (F4-S3)

Another student stated: Counselling builds your mind and brings out a person from the so-called taboos of society(F6-S2). University is the highest institution of education. This is where the turning point comes. As generally speaking, *Career Counselling is an essential concept for university-level students. If he gets counseling about his subject, he will follow the same footsteps that he was guided and be satisfied and successful in practical life.* Career counseling connects students with their future life through proper academic discipline. Few participants believe that it is a combination of degree and career: for example, *If our degree and our career match, then the whole society can utilize its potential* (F6-S1). Hence, University is a mature institution. Here you are an autonomous body. *At this level, a career expert can guide about excellent and positive ambitions of subjects.* But the counselor must be a career specializes and carries both education about careers and training skills.

University is an important platform to counsel students about careers keeping in view their educational record till intermediate. It makes them confident, shows them more and more ways of earning and removes the worries about their future regarding careers. While discussing the advantages of career counseling, few participants highlighted its economic aspects. *Likewise, few students also gave views on the economic aspects of career counselling.* For example, there are two benefits of Career Counselling; it is good from an *earning point of view and excellent from a business perspective.* (F4-S1)

Likewise, one student encouraged career counseling in these words: *Plans are confirmed, confusion is removed, good ideas for higher studies are found.* (F5-S1)

We have degrees but no skills; it bridges the skill gaps; as one of the students said: *Career Counselling bridges the skill gaps.* (F7-S3)

Career counseling gives ideas about career opportunities, subjects, and job scopes to earn sufficient livelihood, leading the whole society towards welfare. Students commented: Also, one student stated: *Career Counselling builds confidence in your earnings and builds caliber in competitions.*(F9-S1)

Theme 3: Difficulties in Career Counselling Services at Universities

Theme 6 examines the difficulties; career counselling can overcome. The theme presented the issues related to their teaching career and students discussed issues related to their academic affairs, which can be alleviated through career counseling. All the participants gave various views on the difficulties career counselling can overcome from the university level student. For example, we are being taught to copy-paste. Complex personalities are being created in the name of the character. This whole process is destroying our trust, and it needs a lot of career counseling. (F1-S1)

Our education system runs religious and general education separately, a person who has received religious education cannot show his ability in public institutions, and similarly, a person who has general education cannot show his ability in religious education institutes; this attitude needs to be balanced as one student stated:

Another problem is that we have to go to a specific place to get career counseling. We have to go to madrassas for guidance on religion and general sectors; now, those who don't have much resources or awareness will miss counseling. (F3-S3)

One of the focus group participants highlighted the general behavior of our education system in which language our curriculum has to be designed. Also, these curriculum issues have to be sorted out through counseling:

A big problem is a curriculum; there is a big difference between our curriculum and social attitudes during Corvid 19. (S2-S4)

In the above themes, all the participants gave mixed views and highlighted critical aspects regarding the difficulties counseling can overcome. The most common sub-themes which emerged from theme 6 were *Unavailability of Careers, Social Pressures, Finance Issues, and Student's difficulties regarding teacher's behaviors. And other less common themes included Class Discrimination and male and female Discriminations. Participants argued, suggested and reported on different issues they were facing. Today's youth is under pressure. Family pressures, society pressures, and then the pressure of grades or less CGPA in studies. Parents pressurize how to get a job. Due to this pressure and due to the fear of not getting a job exact after completing the degree, people go under depression and most of the students commit suicide due to such pressures.*

There are pressure groups in our society, pressure from parents at home, pressure from society, pressure from fellows, pressure from teachers, pressure from job scope and pressure of science studies during Corvid 19. (F5-S1)

It is found the majority of students were disturbed due to the parent's pressure for subject choosing, for example, one student said: Some students get admission in a particular department under the pressure of parents, siblings or friends but they get disturbed when they find out that their interest is zero, then when they can't get good grades, the system does not accept it and psychological issues begin to occur (F5-S1).

Also, the biggest problem nowadays is that the whole world is in a financial crunch due to Covid-19. Many problems associated with this issue are appearing. Jobs are not available. Businesses are closed. In this situation, some skills need to be learned. One student also stated: Most students excel in practical, fieldwork, technical work and vocational type work; they are pushed under the weight of books instead of carrying them according to their mindset, which weakens their abilities. (F7-S2)

Another added:

Everyone is crying about not getting a job; in this situation, it is necessary to polish other skills like sewing, embroidery, or computer expertise. (F10-S1)

Finance is the biggest issue in our region. The majority of people think that our main requirement is bread, cloth and house. Most of the people come from the lower middle class; by paying hefty fees, they only want to earn a living as soon as they complete their degree.

Students gave extreme opinions to highlight this point. For example:

Due to lack of counseling, a field is chosen that cannot be continued later due to a lack of resources. (F5-S5)

Another student raises the point about finance issue as:

Another big problem is finance, Students from middle-class homes like ours apply to different departments of different faculties after FSC. If that student is admitted in a field in which he has no interest, he is forced to take admission so that his fee and year are not wasted. (F4-S2)

A student highlighted the same problem:

Some people choose a problematic field to complete, and some are unable to choose the field they are interested in due to a lack of resources. (F7-S3)

Also, a student from F10 stated that: *Some students are studying compulsorily because they do not have enough money and resources to get admission in any subject other than this degree. (F10-S1)*

Few students reported their problems related to teachers' behavior and they are facing those problems as Teachers highlight their mistakes but don't correct them. Therefore, students have to face all these problems in practical life (F8-S1).

A male student from F4 highlighted a big issue of male and female discrimination in our society. We live in a man dominated society. There are different career counseling scopes for males and females. The system does not allow girls to do fieldwork or research. (F4-S3)

Another male student from F7 highlighted the same issue in these words: *In our environment, Career planning is still done for males but not for females, because they think that investing in females will benefit another house, not us.* (F7-S4)

Thus, I summed it up through participants' responses that *our society has set job standards. Doctors, lawyers, Engineers, Bankers are considered respected, but Mechanics or technicians are not given due respect in our society. Also, the parameter of success is made only science subjects now a day, we have told the children that those who do not study science will fail in life.* Somewhere there is a lack of Career Counselling and unavailability of people involved in career counseling. And this is the reason our students go into stress after going to the fields and commit suicide; in some cases, they need to be given confidence in their field. In the above quotes, participants repeatedly showed the need for career counselling at the university level and discussed the different aspects of their difficulties; career counselling can overcome.

Discussions

Counseling is a magnificent creation of this modern period. We live in a fast and changing system. There are several challenges that people face in this world that are hard to comply with. We get on with our lives most of the time, but occasionally we are interrupted in our tracks by an occurrence or problem that we do not have the resources to resolve at the time. Much of the time, we consult with friends and family on managing such challenges in life. But sometimes their assistance isn't enough, or we're too scared to tell them what's upsetting us, or we don't know who to approach for help (McLeod & McLeod, 2003).

The findings show that the perception of students about counseling is apparent. Few participants who gave opinions think that counseling is a valuable activity; it gives easy solutions. In short, counseling is about finding solutions to problems by consulting an expert on matters, clearing one's understanding, clearing one's confusion and improving one's adjustment in society.

The privies literature also supports my findings such as: "Work with persons and relationships that is evolutionary, distress assistance, psychological, directing, or issue solving is referred to as counseling. Counselling's goal is to allow the "client" to "experience, find, and define ways to live that are more rewarding and resourceful"(BAC 1984), (Baron, 2002). Similarly, Burks and Steffle (1979) define counseling as "a professional connection between an expert counselor as well as a client." This is usually a one-on-one connection, though it can occasionally include more than two persons. It is intended to assist clients in better understanding and clarifying their perspectives on their lifespan development and learning to achieve their self-determined objectives through meaningful, possibly the best choices and the settlement of psychological or personality disorders (Adeusi, 2017).

Counseling services in higher education must at the very least be conducted transparently and methodically. Several regulations indicate that the career counseling service is an essential element in the organization of higher education. However, the legal basis for implementing it in higher education is not as complete and detailed as the BK (Counselling guidance) service in the Elementary and Secondary Education Unit (Sujadi, 2018). Students thought that career counseling eliminates students' difficulties in selecting subjects as *counseling, according to Naryana, is a support provided by specialists to persons to enable them to make decisions and decisions about their lives and so effectively adjust to their environment* (Bibi, 2018).

Also, it was reported that it aware students about the purpose of their learning and further influence of this education in their professional existence, How they will produce with their degree, also they gave the view that career counseling *removes conflicts about future planes*, move a person out of despair and hopelessness about career into a more positive direction for his career. It *formulates youth for market and industry* to choose such discipline in their source of earning that has additional employment opportunities. Similarly, the Islamic approaches to career counseling and modern theories also fully support this definition, as Quran mentions in sura Al-Nisa(29). Likewise, as discussed earlier, it is essential to seek and access a livelihood consultation at any stage of life. Especially when one wants to plan one's career properly at a mature level of life, counselling is of utmost importance and need it. Many studies show that consultation and counseling services in higher education are necessary. The counseling assistance procedure for dealing with learning challenges is in high demand and more effective in enhancing learning outcomes (Hayati & Sujadi, 2018). So, according to participants' responses, there is no arguing about its role and importance at University.

Because the University is the point where a student as a mature person comes to finalize their plans about careers, therefore, at the university level, there were very positive and very quality opinions about the role and importance of career counselling, its usefulness and its uses. Because the choices are narrow at the university level, thus there is not much need for career counselling at the university level. It should be done long before university education. On the other hand, students strongly support career counseling at the university level, suggesting that career counseling should be provided at the time of admission and the end of the degree and also during the education; in this situation, university-level students who are having difficulties find it

challenging to acquire professional assistance; thus some of them decide to communicate their concerns with their friends and even on social networking sites (Sujadi, 2018). Thus, students gave suggestions and feedback on the importance and role of career counselling at the university level. Career counseling *finds the hidden capabilities and individual interest, gives ideas for career choice, builds confidence, polishes the skills, etc.* Thus, the current findings specify that the role and importance of career counselling at the university level is supposed as a vital component in developing students.

The students explain the advantage of career counseling positively as it resolves psychological concerns regarding careers, conducts research expansion aptitudes, eliminates uncertainty about the future, etc. Counseling, for example, is the process of assisting a person in understanding himself and his environment. According to ((Shertzer & Stone, 1976), 6 Guidance, as an educational construct, entails the use of a point of view to assist an individual. It relates to the provision of techniques that allow students to understand things, as well as the organization of procedures and processes to achieve a helping connection.

Teachers had a comprehensive perspective on these issues, covering university-level students' issues, industry and market issues, rapidly changing world conditions, as well as new educational policies and syllabus issues, financial issues, and so on were discussed by teachers. Still, in contrast, most of the students' focus was on academic issues, departmental issues, laboratories issues, lack of practical skills, lack of technical skills, confusion of science or arts, etc.

Although few students raised reservations about textbooks and theoretical learning, claiming that they do not foster the development of practical perspectives and technical abilities, which are critical for career planning. The training provided in these programs is intended to teach concepts and facts, which don't include practices that involve students to think, create, and solve issues to prepare them for future points of view regarding interviews and presentations of their work in the industry. As a result, in the current situation, the syllabus and teaching methods do not promote career counseling comprehension.

Not getting a job in a developing country like Pakistan is not a big deal, especially in the current situation of the country in which career issues have increased due to continuous lockdown in covid-19, so in this situation, learning ease, problem-solving skills, improved learning motivation, and mastery of the language of teaching are all important in Higher Education (Sujadi, 2018). There is a need to promote practical skills and technical education to continue their livelihood based on their skills.

Furthermore, social pressure is a big issue in terms of career counseling that the new generation is facing, especially the pressure of parents to study science, the pressure of grades and the pressure of an excellent job from society. Furthermore, the majority of students were obstructive primarily due to teacher behavior. Students are bound to become dissatisfied if they are given no direction in their education. The issue of finance was highlighted as another major issue. Sometimes students choose subjects due to unfamiliarity that they cannot change later due to heavy fees. Sometimes, there is a situation where the student can go to a particular department but can't go because they can't pay hefty fees. In this way, his talent is wasted, but the nation also loses a talented person.

Students were of the view that in our country, where there are many problems in getting a good job, there is also the problem of class discrimination, which was considered a significant issue and needed to be counseled. They argued that many people who got the degree through hard work are often disqualified from the job due to a lack of hi-fi approach and authority. On the other hand, people who are not eligible for that specific post can only approach the authorities often occupy high positions using unfair means.

Conclusions

In every country around the world, career counseling services are an integral part of the educational system. This is especially crucial for a country like Pakistan, which has its ideological foundations in Islam and has many Muslims who are very passionate and loyal to their beliefs. This study aims to look at the role and importance of career counseling as a great need of the hour and it is the only source that can bridge the gaps between students and the industry. Students must be able to face market challenges after getting career counselling at the university level. Data indicates that the students understand the process of career counselling and value the benefit of counselling provided to them for their awareness about various careers.

Moreover, students with diverse backgrounds are still unfamiliar with the term counseling or career counseling. The majority agreed that career counseling at the university level is more critical than all previous levels because this is when their careers have to start correctly. They have to get into the practical field. Completely denied its need at the university level. The majority of students presented their views about the role and importance of career counselling at the university level. *Thus it is concluded is that the qualities among students that they can go to the career counseling services with complete confidence, see the problems, and solve the problems being a benefit of them* during Corvid 19. Therefore, considering the usefulness of career counseling, it needs to be extended to the level so that the new generation can be freed from all kinds of social pressures and other difficulties in making career choices during Corvid 19. Students will be able to decide their careers according to their abilities with confidence and plan their future goals with an independent mindset

beyond the so-called standards of society. It is recommended from the study that career counseling services from all universities *Covid-19 scenario* should promote develop Practical and Technical Skills even during Corvid 19 in addition to Theoretical education, therefore enhancing the employment scope.

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